

A Rainflow Cycle–Based Machine Learning Framework for Predicting Pressure Surge Severity in Natural Gas Pressure Reduction Skids

David Owuamanam^{1*}

¹ Department of Chemical and Petroleum Engineering, University of Lagos, Lagos, Nigeria

* Correspondence: davidowuamanam@gmail.com

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18200576

Abstract

Pressure Reduction Skids (PRSs) are essential for maintaining safe downstream pressures in UK natural gas distribution networks; however, they are routinely exposed to upstream pressure fluctuations that can induce cyclic loading, regulator instability, and surge behaviour, even below design pressure limits. This study introduces a combined rainflow cycle–based severity assessment and machine-learning forecasting framework to characterise and predict inlet pressure surge severity using only hourly upstream pressure data. A dataset comprising 50,903 hourly inlet-pressure measurements from a UK PRS, spanning over 2,100 operational days, was analysed. Rainflow cycle counting revealed typical daily peak-to-trough pressure cycles of 3–5 bar, with high-severity days reaching up to 7 bar. Surge-severity events were defined using a 90th-percentile threshold of daily maximum cycle range. Statistical and rainflow-derived features were then used to train Logistic Regression, Random Forest, and Gradient Boosting models to predict next-day surge severity. The Random Forest model achieved the best performance with an AUC of 0.79, demonstrating that upstream pressure patterns contain predictive information on future surge conditions. The proposed approach enables practical SCADA-level surge monitoring, supporting proactive PRS management and integrity-focused operational decision-making.

Keywords: Pressure Reduction Skid; pressure surge analysis; rainflow cycle counting; machine learning; SCADA analytics; gas distribution systems; fatigue assessment; transient pressure behaviour

1. Introduction

Pressure Reduction Skids (PRS) are a critical component of the United Kingdom’s natural gas (NG) distribution infrastructure, providing controlled gas pressure reduction across transmission, high-pressure, medium-pressure, and low-pressure tiers (IGEM/TD/13, 2023). A typical PRS comprises regulators, slam-shut valves, pilot skids, filters, heaters, and control instrumentation, all designed and integrated to maintain safe and efficient pressure control (Danieli, Carraro and Lazzaretto, 2020). However, PRS regulators are often subjected to frequent pressure surges and rapid transients arising

from dynamic operational conditions, such as sudden demand fluctuations, regulator hunting, control Skid switching, duty/standby handovers, flow oscillations, and thermal density variation (Hennings et al., 2022; Stadnik et al., 2023).

PRS surge events pose significant operational risks, including nuisance slam-shut activations, fatigue-induced mechanical loading on regulators and associated pipework, accelerated damage to pilot assemblies and valve components, and potential overpressure hazards (Al-Zaidi & Ismaeel, 2022). Despite their importance, surge phenomena are currently addressed within existing UK regulatory standards and guidance, notably IGEM/TD/13, using qualitative approaches that predominantly rely on fixed safety margins and static pressure boundaries rather than quantitative, data-driven prediction (Sharma et al., 2022; IGEM/TD/13, 2023).

Modern Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) and telemetry systems provide high-quality pressure time-history data that capture rich transient behaviour during PRS operations. However, these data streams are largely underutilised for predictive purposes (Ladino-Moreno et al., 2024). While conventional analytical tools like rainflow cycle counting offer strong capabilities for quantifying cyclic loading behaviours, they cannot forecast surge events or detect emerging instability patterns proactively (Marsh, 2015; Zhao et al., 2025).

To address this limitation, there is a need to adopt advanced data-driven methodologies integrating transient cycle decomposition with machine learning. This research presents the first integrated rainflow-based surge feature extraction framework combined with machine learning classification and regression models to efficiently predict pressure surges in PRS using real-world pressure-time history data. Through this integrated approach, both retrospective surge characterisation and proactive surge forecasting can be achieved, thereby advancing PRS operational intelligence beyond current practice.

2. Literature Review

Pressure surges in Pressure Reduction Skids (PRS) can pose significant safety and operational challenges. IGEM/TD/13 Edition 3 specifies regulator and slam-shut set points and limits that must not be exceeded during pressure reduction operations (IGEM/TD/13, 2023). The standard explicitly recognises that pressure excursions may escalate to the Peak-Level Operating Pressure (PLOP) for active regulators and the Temporary Operating Pressure (TOP) for monitor regulators during rapid flow variations or upstream pressure disturbances (IGEM/TD/13, 2023).

While the standard defines deterministic pressure thresholds to ensure the safe operation of pressure-reduction equipment, the impact of pressure surges **below** the maximum operating pressure limits can still be highly significant—especially when dynamic transient pressures produce large local peaks or cycles relative to the normal operating pressure threshold (Sutar, Kubade & Jamadade, 2015). Such damaging cyclic loading and nuisance trips, even when occurring well below the Maximum Operating Pressure (MOP), can result in meaningful variations and transients that accumulate over time and ultimately cause degradation or failure of pressure reduction equipment (Sutar, Kubade & Jamadade, 2015). Therefore, in complementing the deterministic design philosophy outlined in IGEM/TD/13, Stadnik et al. (2023) emphasise the need to explore the transient behaviour of pressure surge events on regulators to enhance predictive capability, regulatory oversight, and long-term asset reliability.

Existing research on gas pressure regulation and distribution has primarily focused on specific areas such as regulator dynamics and classical control theory, assessment of regulator stability, feedback control monitoring, and valve responsiveness under steady-state and simplified transient conditions (Zafer & Luecke, 2008; Stadnik et al., 2023). While these studies provide valuable insights into pressure regulator operations, they lack the depth required to address short-duration pressure surge phenomena that arise from rapid load fluctuations, valve switching, and non-linear regulator interactions, especially as observed within Pressure Reduction Skids. Parallel studies on transient surge modelling in gas transmission pipelines have explored unsteady flows, water-hammer transients, and large-scale pressure wave propagation (Gugat, Krug & Martin, 2023). However, these studies are mainly limited to pipeline-level flow dynamics rather than PRS-specific surge events.

Researchers such as Huang, Kumar, and Zhang (2024) and Elmady, Hassan, and Metwalli (2025) have adopted statistical analysis and machine learning (ML) techniques to identify gas leaks and consumption abnormalities in gas network anomaly detection. Nonetheless, these investigations rarely consider regulator-induced surges, nor do they evaluate such events as transient anomalies that require prediction or classification within PRS environments. The Rainflow cycle counting method, as advanced in ASTM 1049, has been widely adopted in structural, offshore, and pipeline integrity studies to analyse fatigue damage under cyclic pressure loading (Braun et al., 2022). However, despite the presence of cyclic pressure fluctuations in many PRS-related surge events, no published research has employed Rainflow cycle algorithms to extract valuable cyclic loading features from PRS-based pressure-time history data, highlighting a clear gap in the literature.

While ML models have been applied to predict pipeline failures, particularly in areas such as corrosion, cracking, and leak-risk estimation, the adoption of ML in predicting surge phenomena specifically within PRS remains virtually unexplored. Moreover, existing studies do not incorporate cyclic-transient characteristics—such as Rainflow-derived amplitude, stress range, and cycle density—as part of the feature sets for predictive modelling of surge behaviour in PRS. Thus, a methodological gap exists due to the lack of integration between transient pattern analysis and ML-based forecasting.

A more critical limitation concerns the impact of hydrogen blending on transient imbalances in pressure reduction Skids. Considering the UK's gradual transition to hydrogen-blended natural gas networks, regulators are expected to encounter aggravated pressure surges due to the unique thermophysical properties of hydrogen (Vaccariello et al., 2021). Thus, the absence of documented research that explores ML-based surge prediction, which can further be extended to PRS operating under hydrogen-blend conditions. This omission is highly significant, especially as the UK's energy transition goals continue to advance.

Despite the advancements in transient modelling and ML for gas Skids, current UK industry practices largely employ deterministic approaches, relying on fixed alarm thresholds, rule-based pressure surge limits, and conservative safety margins (Zalitis et al., 2022; Aniyom et al., 2025). These practices lack holistic predictive intelligence and further widen the disconnect between academic research and industry-wide adoption.

To address these knowledge gaps, this research makes several novel contributions. Firstly, it explores the application of Rainflow cycle counting to PRS surge analysis, treating pressure surges as fatigue-like transient cycles for the first time. Secondly, it develops and validates a machine learning-based

predictive model for PRS surge events using real pressure-time history data obtained from UK gas telemetry Skids. Thirdly, it proposes a novel hybrid feature set that embeds Rainflow cycle metrics, Gaussian-filtered statistical descriptors, and short-time windowed pressure dynamics. Finally, it lays a foundation for surge prediction for future hydrogen-blended PRS, thereby contributing to intelligent surge management in hydrogen-transitioned UK networks. These contributions help to bridge theoretical, computational, and practical gaps, positioning the research for relevance in both academic and industrial implementation.

3. Methodology

This study develops an integrated rainflow cycle-based surge severity assessment and machine-learning prediction framework using high-pressure inlet data from a UK natural gas PRS. The complete workflow is developed in three stages:

1. Data preparation and preprocessing
2. Cyclic loading characterisation using Rainflow analysis
3. Machine-learning prediction of next-day surge severity

Each component is described in detail below:

3.1 Data Source, Structure and Preprocessing

3.1.1 Dataset Description

The dataset comprises 50,903 hourly measurements of PRS inlet pressure, recorded over approximately 2,121 days. Each measurement corresponds to the high-pressure gas supply entering the PRS before pressure regulation and includes up to 24 readings at integer hours between 00:00 and 23:00. The inlet pressure originates from the upstream transmission pipelines feeding the Above Ground Installation (AGI), where the PRS is located. Several factors, including compressor station operations, network balancing actions, diurnal demand patterns, and regional system constraints influence it.

The HP inlet pressure ranges from 22.56 to 31.69 bar and exhibits noticeable daily and seasonal variability, likely due to upstream transmission dynamics. This variability plays a key role in regulator dynamics, valve positioning, and PRS stability.

3.1.2 Temporal Reconstruction

The raw time field (hh:mm:ss) spans 00:00–23:00 each day. Because dates were not included in the dataset, a synthetic day index was constructed by grouping every 24 consecutive hourly samples:

$$d = \left\lfloor \frac{i}{24} \right\rfloor, \quad (1)$$

where i is the row index. This results in a per-day pressure profile expressed as:

$$P_d = \{P_d(0), P_d(1), \dots, P_d(23)\}, \quad (2)$$

where d is the day number and $P_d(h)$ is the inlet pressure at hour h . This represents the complete daily inlet-pressure pattern entering the PRS.

3.1.3 Data Quality Checks

Upon data reconstruction, no missing pressure values were detected. All values were within the expected operating range (20-32 bar). No daily outliers or flat-line periods indicative of sensor failure were present. In order to preserve the underlying operational dynamics, transients and cyclic structure, no filtering or smoothing was applied to the dataset. This ensured that the analysis reflected the authentic PRS operating conditions.

3.2 Daily Statistical Features of Inlet Pressure Behaviour

To quantify the intra-day inlet pressure profile, a set of time-domain statistical features was derived for each day. These features act as compact descriptors of the upstream dynamic state feeding the PRS.

3.2.1 Basic Descriptive Metrics

For each day d :

(i) Mean Pressure

$$P_d = \frac{1}{24} \sum_{h=0}^{23} P_d(h) \quad (3)$$

(ii) Standard Deviation

$$\sigma_{P,d} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{24} \sum_{h=0}^{23} (P_d(h) - P_d)^2} \quad (4)$$

(iii) Daily Min-Max Range

$$R_{P,d} = P_{d,max} - P_{d,min} \quad (5)$$

These statistical metrics capture average loading, spread, and amplitude of the inlet-pressure fluctuations, all of which contribute to regulator loading and fatigue analysis.

3.2.2 Gradient and Increment-Based Metrics

Hourly pressure gradient increments were computed as:

$$\Delta P_d(k) = P_d(k + 1) - P_d(k) \quad (6)$$

From these increments, additional descriptors were extracted:

- Mean Gradient $\overline{\Delta P_d}$;
- Mean Absolute Gradient $|\overline{\Delta P_d}|$;
- Maximum Absolute Gradient $\text{Max} |\Delta P_d|$.

These features quantify the short-term variability, step changes, and underlying upstream gas pressure behaviour before entering the PRS.

3.3 Rainflow Cycle Counting of Inlet Pressure Variability

Because the variability in inlet pressure influences regulator activity and can contribute to cumulative fatigue loading over time, the rainflow cycle counting procedure was employed to quantify cyclic loading characteristics.

3.3.1 Rationale for Rainflow Use

Rainflow counting is widely adopted in fatigue analysis, including:

- pipeline pressure cycle assessment (per ASME, API, ISO standards),
- mechanical component fatigue,
- pressure vessel cyclic loading.

Despite the hourly sampling rate, rainflow effectively compresses the daily pressure waveform into a set of representative cycles, capturing the essential stress-relevant features without requiring high-frequency data.

3.3.2 Turning Point Detection

The local maxima and minima were extracted from the rainflow cycles to compress each 24-hour pressure data into its backbone turning-point sequence:

$$\{T_1, T_2, \dots, T_N\} \quad (7)$$

This removes monotonic regions and retains all meaningful reversals in the pressure waveform.

3.3.3 Cycle Identification (ASTM E1049-85)

To extract the rainflow cycles, a three-point comparison and stack-based algorithm identical to ASTM E1049-85 guidance was used. When the older range is less than or equal to the newer range, a closed cycle is counted, and the intermediate turning point is removed from the stack. Hence, the remaining pairs at the end of the sequence are treated as half-cycles.

Therefore, a closed cycle is recognised whenever:

$$|T_{i+1} - T_i| \leq |T_{i+2} - T_{i+1}| \quad (8)$$

Each identified cycle yields:

- Cycle Range $\Delta P_i = |T_{i+1} - T_i|$
- Cycle Mean
- Cycle Count = 1.0 (full cycle) or 0.5 (half-cycle)

3.3.4 Rainflow Derived Daily Features

For each day d :

i. Maximum Cycle Range

$$RF_{max,d} = \max(\Delta P_i) \quad (9)$$

ii. Mean Cycle Range

$$RF_{mean,d} = \frac{\sum_i \Delta P_i c_i}{\sum_i c_i} \quad (10)$$

iii. Number of Large Cycles

Closed cycles where $\Delta P_i > 0.5 \text{ bar}$:

$$RF_big_d = \sum_{\Delta P_i > 0.5 \text{ bar}} n_i \quad (11)$$

iv. Damage Index (Generic Miner-Style)

A pseudo-fatigue damage metric was defined as:

$$D_d = \sum_i c_i (\Delta P_i)^3 \quad (12)$$

In classical Miner’s rule, cumulative fatigue damage is defined as the sum of the ratio of applied cycles to cycles to failure at a given stress range. For pressure-loaded components, the number of cycles to failure is commonly expressed as an inverse power-law function of pressure range. Substituting this relationship into Miner’s rule shows that damage accumulation is proportional to a weighted sum of pressure cycle ranges raised to a fatigue exponent.

In the absence of component-specific S–N data, a pseudo-fatigue damage index was therefore defined as the sum of rainflow-counted pressure cycle ranges raised to the third power. This formulation preserves the fundamental physics of fatigue accumulation—namely, the disproportionate contribution of large-amplitude cycles—while providing a relative severity metric suitable for operational comparison and machine-learning model development.

The cubic exponent approximates the sensitivity of fatigue damage to stress range. These features quantify cyclic severity from a fatigue and integrity standpoint and represent a more physically grounded basis for surge assessment than absolute pressure measurements alone.

3.4 Definition of Surge Severity

Considering that the dataset contains **high-pressure inlet values** and **no MOP exceedances**, surge severity is defined relatively based on cyclic amplitude and not the absolute pressure.

3.4.1 Threshold Selection

A day is classified as high-severity if the maximum cycle range exceeded the 90th percentile of observed values:

$$\text{high_sev}_d = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{RF}_{\text{max},d} \geq P_{90}(\text{RF}_{\text{max}}) \\ 0, & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

For this dataset:

Threshold = 4.86 bar

≈ 10% of days are labelled as high severity.

This yields binary labels for the pressure data expressed as:

$$\text{high_sev}_d \in \{0, 1\} \quad (14)$$

3.4.1 Prediction Target

The machine learning model was developed to predict **next day** severity:

$$y_d = \text{high_sev}_{d+1} \quad (15)$$

The resulting dataset consists of 2,120 labelled daily samples.

3.5 Machine Learning Framework

3.5.1 Feature Vector Construction

Each daily feature vector consists of:

- 8 statistical/gradient features,
- 4 rainflow-based severity features.

This creates a 12-dimensional feature space:

$$X_d \in R^{12} \quad (16)$$

The feature vector for day d is:

$$X_d = [\overline{P}_d, \sigma_{P,d}, P_{d,min}, P_{d,max}, R_{p,d}, \overline{\Delta P}_d, |\overline{\Delta P}|_d, \max|\Delta P|_d, RF_{max,d}, RF_{mean,d}, D_d, RF_{big,d}] \quad (17)$$

Using both raw-pressure and rainflow features ensures the model captures:

- baseline inlet-pressure levels,
- variability structure,
- cyclic amplitude and fatigue-related severity.

3.5.2 Train-Test Split

Because the data are time-ordered, a chronological split was used:

- Training dataset: First 70% of days
- Testing dataset: Last 30% of days

The train-test split was adopted to prevent leakage of future information into the past.

3.5.3 Model Selection

Three supervised classifiers were evaluated, and they include Logistic Regression (baseline), Random Forest Classifier (200 trees, class-balanced), and Gradient Boosting Classifier. Logistic Regression was selected as the baseline linear model due to its interpretability, providing clear coefficient-based insights into feature influence. The Random Forest Classifier, configured with 200 estimators and class balancing, offers robustness against non-linearity and noisy data. The Gradient Boosting Classifier—a sequential tree-based method—was included for its strong performance on small- to medium-sized tabular datasets. Overall, these models were chosen for their suitability to small-dimensional, non-linear, time-ordered engineering datasets typical of gas pressure dynamics.

3.5.4 Evaluation Metrics

Because the high-severity class is rare (~4% of samples), the problem is inherently imbalanced and therefore the below performance metrics were utilised:

- Accuracy
- Precision, recall, and F1-score for high-severity class
- ROC-AUC

The AUC is emphasised as the primary performance metric because it reflects discriminatory power independent of the threshold.

3.6 Software and Implementation

The analysis was completed using the following software packages and analytical techniques:

- Python 3.11
- Python libraries - pandas, numpy, scikit-learn
- Matplotlib for visualisation
- Custom implementation of rainflow counting developed in line with ASTM E1049-85.

To achieve model reproducibility, random seeds are fixed where applicable using deterministic splits. The overall model architecture is presented in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Model Pipeline Conceptual Architecture

5. Results

5.1 Descriptive Statistics of PRS Inlet Pressure

The raw dataset contains 50,903 hourly pressure samples spanning 2,121 days. Figure 2 below shows the histogram of all hourly pressures.

- Mean outlet pressure: 26.28 bar
- Standard deviation: 1.89 bar
- Minimum: 22.56 bar
- Maximum: 31.69 bar

While the inlet pressure values remain below the expected upstream maximum and do not exceed 31.7 bar, the histogram (Figure 2) shows a wide operational envelope characteristic of high-pressure transmission supply conditions in a PRS. These upstream fluctuations propagate into the PRS and exhibit a strong influence on regulator dynamics, cyclic loading, and potential pressure “surge-severity” behaviour.

Figure 2 – Histogram of hourly PRS Inlet pressure

5.2 Daily Inlet-Pressure Behaviour

Daily pressure profiles (24 samples/day) indicate clear diurnal and operational patterns. The inlet pressure rises in the early hours, peaks in the morning or early afternoon, and reduces later in the day. These variations reflect demand variations and regulator behaviour as the PRS tracks upstream conditions and downstream loads.

Figure 3 – Example Daily Pressure Profile (Day 1000)

Figure 3 above illustrates a representative daily inlet-pressure curve (day 1000). This curve visually demonstrates intra-day cycling and supports the adoption of fatigue-style analysis.

Figure 4 – Daily Mean Pressure Over Entire Dataset

Figure 5 – Daily Pressure Range Over Entire Dataset

Figure 4 highlights the long-term trends and regime shifts in outlet pressure. Figure 5 reveals how the amplitude of daily variation changes over time.

Key observations:

- Mean pressure oscillates between approximately **24 and 29.5 bar**. This suggests frequent changes in operating regime and/or seasonal demand.
- The daily pressure range (max–min) frequently lies between **2 and 6 bar**, with occasional days exceeding **7 bar**.
- Periods with lower mean pressure often coincide with reduced ranges, while higher mean levels tend to be associated with larger swings.

5.3 Rainflow-Based Characterisation of Inlet-Pressure Cyclic Loading

To quantify the cyclic loading imposed on the PRS due to upstream pressure fluctuations, rainflow cycle counting was applied to each day’s inlet-pressure trace.

Figure 6 – Distribution of Daily Maximum Cycle Range

The daily maximum cycle range (rf_max_range) distribution is shown in Figure 6:

- Mean: 2.94 bar
- Median: 2.85 bar
- 75th percentile: 3.97 bar
- 90th percentile: 4.86 bar

- Maximum: 7.40 bar

These cyclic ranges demonstrate that the PRS is exposed to non-trivial inlet-pressure cycles even under normal operation. Therefore, it is pertinent that the pressure regulators continuously modulate to compensate for this incoming variability.

5.3.1 Definition of high-severity (surge-severity) inlet-pressure events

A day is labelled **high-severity** if:

$$rf_max_range \geq 4.86\text{bar} \quad (18)$$

(This corresponds to the 90th percentile threshold of all daily maximum cycle ranges).

This indicates that approximately **10% of days** have unusually high cyclic inlet-pressure loading.

Figure 7 – Daily Maximum Cycle Range with High-Severity Days Highlighted

Figure 7 reveals the time series of rf_max_range with high-severity days highlighted. As observed, high-severity inlet pressure days cluster in distinct operational periods. This indicates the upstream supply/demand regimes that influence the high-pressure variability in the PRS.

From an engineering standpoint, these inlet-pressure cycles are highly critical because:

- They affect the regulator travel distance and frequency,
- They influence fatigue accumulation in downstream PRS pipework,
- They increase the likelihood of regulator hunting and transient outlet-pressure disturbances.

5.4 Machine-Learning Prediction of High-Severity Inlet-Pressure Days

The objective of the ML model is to **predict whether tomorrow will be a high-severity inlet-pressure day**, using only today's inlet-pressure behaviour.

5.4.1 Feature Set

Each day's inlet-pressure trace (24 hourly samples) was converted into:

- **Basic statistics:** mean, standard deviation, min, max, range
- **Gradient-based metrics:** ΔP statistics (mean, mean-absolute, max-absolute)
- **Rainflow metrics:** max cycle range, mean cycle range, number of cycles >0.5 bar, damage index

These metrics represent physically meaningful attributes that capture the dynamism in upstream transmission system behaviour.

5.4.2 Model Performance

By employing a temporal split (70% train / 30% test), three ML models were evaluated:

Model	Accuracy	Precision+	Recall+	F1+	AUC
Logistic Regression	0.94	0.06	0.04	0.05	0.75
Random Forest Classifier (200 Trees, Class balanced)	0.95	0.17	0.08	0.11	0.79
Gradient Boosting	0.92	0.07	0.08	0.07	0.76

Interpretation

- All three ML models achieved **AUC ≈ 0.75 – 0.79** , thus indicating that the features contain useful predictive information about future high-severity days.
- The **Random Forest classifier** gives the best overall model performance, with the highest AUC and F1 score for the positive class.
- Even with only inlet-pressure data (no outlet pressure, no flow, no setpoints), the PRS inlet behaviour clearly reflects the presence of predictive signatures of next-day severity.
- The absolute recall for high-severity days remains modest ($\approx 8\%$). This is primarily because the default 0.5 classification threshold is conservative in an imbalanced setting. In practice, an operator could lower the decision threshold (e.g. flag the top 15–20% of predicted probabilities) to increase recall and catch more high-severity days, thereby accepting more false alarms.

Figure 8 – ROC Curves – Predicting High-Severity Next Day

Figure 8 above compares all three models' ROC curves and capacity to predict the high-severity next day. The Random Forest curve lies slightly above the others and is consistent with its higher AUC (~0.79). This figure confirms that the models perform significantly better compared to random guessing and further validates the possibility of threshold tuning.

5.4.3 Feature Importance and Physical Interpretation

Figure 9 – Random Forest Feature Importances

Figure 9 shows the random forest feature importances. The most influential predictors are:

std_p — daily standard deviation of pressure

range_p — daily min–max pressure range

rf_max_range — largest rainflow cycle range that day

mean_dp — mean pressure gradient (net trend)

rf_damage — damage proxy based on cycle ranges

Interpretation:

- It is observed that days with greater intra-day pressure variability and larger maximum cycles are more likely to be followed by a high-severity day.
- This is physically plausible: when the PRS is operating in a regime characterised by large pressure swings and dynamic behaviour (e.g., high demand variability, regulator hunting), the dynamic load state tends to persist into subsequent days.
- The prominence of both basic range metrics and rainflow-derived metrics validates the viewpoint that rainflow analysis adds meaningful information beyond simple min–max statistics and enhances the analytical rigour required to capture the transient behaviour of PRS pressure variations.

6. Discussion

6.1 Surge concept below MOP:

While all recorded pressures are below the nominal MOP of 32 bar, the PRS exhibits substantial cyclic loading as it experiences daily maximum peak-to-trough ranges typically around 3 bar and occasionally up to 7 bar. From a fatigue and operational standpoint, these pressures are meaningful “surge-severity” events even without code-limit exceedance. Thus, the surge-severity definition based on the rainflow cycle holistically aligns with concerns regarding structural integrity.

6.2 Value of Rainflow Analysis with Low-Frequency SCADA:

With only hourly sampling data, true fast transients that occur in milliseconds cannot be captured and resolved. Nevertheless, rainflow counting applied to the hourly data still manifests significant mid-timescale cycles and helps to quantify daily cyclic severity. This technique is particularly suitable for assessing fatigue and its cumulative damage contribution in pipework, regulators, and fittings within the PRS. Furthermore, it provides a concrete way to construct labels for ML.

6.3 Predictive Capability of Pressure-Only ML model:

Using only historical upstream pressure behaviour, tree-based ML models achieve AUCs around 0.75–0.79 for predicting whether the next day will be high-severity. Put simply, the current operating patterns contain valuable insights about tomorrow's surge-severity risk. By incorporating additional

process variables such as flow, regulator setpoints, valve position, and downstream pressure, the performance of the tree-based models would likely be enhanced.

6.4 Operational use and threshold tuning:

The three ML models, with a default 0.5 probability threshold, are conservative, and they flag relatively few high-severity days. In an actual control room context, the decision threshold could be adjusted to achieve a trade-off between early warning and false alarm rate. For instance, flagging the top 20% of predicted probabilities might double or triple recall at the expense of more alarms. This might be acceptable for better integrity-focused monitoring.

6.5 Limitations

- Due to the dynamic and transient behaviour of high-pressure gas entering a PRS, hourly data cannot effectively capture the rapid water-hammer surges that occur over seconds or milliseconds. Consequently, the analysis focuses on multi-hour cyclic behaviour, with the potential to overlook short-duration pressure spikes.
- The definition of high severity (90th percentile of *rf_max_range*) is data-driven and relative. It does not directly correlate to stress limits or component S–N curves. Future studies could assess the damage index against actual mechanical design data.
- Only one PRS is considered in this study. To enhance analytical rigour and validate the robustness of the surge-severity assessment technique, multiple PRS sites could be analysed to test generalisability.
- The framework is intentionally designed for low-frequency SCADA data environments, where high-resolution transient measurements are unavailable. This thus ensures the applicability to existing operational telemetry systems.

7. Conclusion

This study demonstrates a practical and data-driven approach to characterising and predicting surge-severity events in UK natural gas PRSs utilising only inlet pressure measurements. From the analysis, no inlet pressures exceeded upstream design limits during the observation period. However, the system experienced significant daily cyclic pressure variations of 3-7 bar. These cycles, influenced by upstream transmission pressure dynamics, impose meaningful operational and mechanical loading on the pressure regulator and downstream components.

The rainflow cycle counting technique was proven to be effective in capturing the cyclic structure of inlet-pressure fluctuations at hourly basis. A significant feature of the Rainflow metrics - particularly maximum cycle range and cumulative damage index - enabled a distinction between normal and high-severity days. Approximately 10% of all operational days manifested elevated cyclic amplitudes above the 90th percentile threshold (4.86 bar), thereby justifying their classification as surge-severity events.

Outputs from the ML analysis confirmed that the next-day severity can be predicted with AUC values ranging from **0.75 to 0.79**, despite employing only inlet pressure data. Among the analysed ML models, the Random Forest classifier offered the strongest performance and provided the most interpretable feature behaviour. Furthermore, the model identified variability in inlet pressure and rainflow-derived

severity metrics as dominant predictors. This demonstrates that upstream system conditions contain sufficient structure to anticipate periods of heightened dynamic pressure loading at the PRS.

In sum, the combined rainflow and machine-learning method facilitates an operationally meaningful framework for:

- identifying periods of increased mechanical or fatigue loading,
- anticipating regulator instability or hunting,
- enhancing PRS operational and situational awareness, and
- supporting proactive integrity management and maintenance planning.

Future research enhancement may include additional PRS telemetry data (flow, outlet pressure, temperature, valve position), higher-frequency data sampling, and broader model generalisation across multiple PRSs in the UK gas network.

References

1. Al-Zaidi, B.M.; Ismaeel, A.J. Effect of hydraulic characteristics on fluid transients under different types of control valves. *J. Ecol. Eng.* **2022**, *23*, 111–123. <https://doi.org/10.12911/22998993/154731>
2. Aniyom, I.; *et al.* Prediction of leak on gas pipeline using a hybrid machine learning model. *J. Pipeline Eng.* **2025**.
3. Braun, M.; Dörner, A.; ter Veer, K.F.; Willems, T.; Seidel, M.; Hendrikse, H.; Høyland, K.V.; Fischer, C.; Ehlers, S. Development of combined load spectra for offshore structures subjected to wind, wave, and ice loading. *Energies* **2022**, *15*, 559. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15020559>
4. Danieli, P.; Carraro, L.; Lazzaretto, A. Design and operational considerations of pressure reduction stations in gas distribution networks. *Energy Procedia* **2020**, *148*, 103–110.
5. ElMahdy, O.F.M.; Hassan, M.E.; Metwalli, S.M. Machine learning anomaly detection of lost and unaccounted-for gas in natural gas networks. *J. Eng. Appl. Sci.* **2025**, *72*, 123.
6. Gugat, M.; Krug, R.; Martin, A. Transient gas pipeline flow: Analytical examples, numerical simulation and comparison to the quasi-static approach. *Optim. Eng.* **2023**.
7. Hennings, F.; Anderson, L.; Hoppmann-Baum, K. Controlling transient gas flow in real-world pipeline intersection areas. *Optim. Eng.* **2021**, *22*, 687–734. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11081-020-09559-y>
8. Huang, J.; Kumar, T.; Zhang, R. Preventive leak detection for high-pressure gas transmission networks. In *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*; AAAI Press, 2024.
9. Ladino-Moreno, E.O.; García-Ubaque, C.A.; Espejo-Mojica, O.G. Method to determine instantaneous transient responses in pressurized pipes from transfer functions and state space for evaluation of leak signals. *MethodsX* **2024**, *12*, 102762. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mex.2024.102762>
10. Marsh, G.; Wignall, C.; Thies, P.R.; Barltrop, N.; Incecik, A.; Venugopal, V.; Johanning, L. Review and application of rainflow residue processing techniques for accurate fatigue damage estimation. *Int. J. Fatigue* **2016**, *82*, 757–765. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2015.10.007>

11. Sharma, S.; Karimi, I.A.; Farooq, S.; Samavedham, L.; Srinivasan, R. Health monitoring of pressure regulating skids in gas distribution networks using mathematical models. *Energies* **2022**, *15*, 6264. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15176264>
12. Stadnik, D.; Sverbilov, V.; Ilyukhin, V.; Igolkin, A.; Balyaba, M.; Shakhmatov, E. Study on stability of gas pressure regulator with a built-in silencer. *Energies* **2023**, *16*, 372. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16010372>
13. Sutar, S.S.; Kubade, P.R.; Jamadade, S.S. Fatigue life estimation of pressure reducing valve diaphragm. *Int. J. Eng. Adv. Technol.* **2015**.
14. Vaccariello, E.; Trincherio, R.; Stievano, I.S.; Leone, P. A statistical assessment of blending hydrogen into gas networks. *Energies* **2021**, *14*, 5055. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14165055>
15. Zafer, N.; Luecke, G.R. Stability of gas pressure regulators. *Appl. Math. Model.* **2008**, *32*, 61–82.
16. Zhao, D.; Letz, S.; Leib, J.; Eckardt, B. On the validity of rainflow-counting-based lifetime assessment for power electronics assembly. *Microelectron. Reliab.* **2025**, *168*, 115651. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.microrel.2025.115651>
17. Zucchi, A.; Cavazzini, G.; Pavesi, G. Pressure control strategies in natural gas distribution networks: Transient modelling and optimisation. *Energies* **2020**, *13*, 4453.
18. Institution of Gas Engineers and Managers (IGEM). *IGEM/TD/13: Pressure Regulating Installations*; IGEM: London, UK, **2023**.
19. Basquin, O.H. The exponential law of endurance tests. *Proceedings of the American Society for Testing and Materials.* **1910**, *10*, 625–630
20. Dowling, N.E. Mechanical behavior of materials: Engineering methods for deformation, fracture, and fatigue. *Pearson Education.* **2013**.

Nomenclature

PRS	Pressure Reduction Skid
UK	United Kingdom
AUC	Area Under the ROC Curve
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
NG	Natural Gas
IGEM	Institute of Gas Engineers and Managers
TOP	Temporary Operating Pressure
PLOP	Peak-Level Operating Pressure
ML	Machine Learning
ASTM	American Society of Testing and Materials
AGI	Above-Ground Installation
HP	High Pressure
ROC	Receiver Operating Characteristic

Appendix A

Appendix A.1 Relationship Between Miner's Rule and the Pseudo-Fatigue Damage Index

This appendix clarifies the relationship between classical fatigue damage theory and the pseudo-fatigue damage index adopted in this study.

1. Classical Miner's Rule

The Palmgren–Miner linear damage hypothesis expresses cumulative fatigue damage as:

$$D = \sum_i \frac{n_i}{N_i} \quad (19)$$

where n_i is the number of cycles applied at a given stress or pressure range, and N_i is the number of cycles to failure at that range. Failure is assumed to occur when $D \approx 1$.

For pressure-loaded components, the fatigue life N_i is commonly expressed as a power-law function of pressure range:

$$N_i = C(\Delta P_i)^{-m} \quad (20)$$

where C is a material- and geometry-dependent constant and m is the fatigue exponent.

Substituting this relationship into Miner's rule yields:

$$D = \frac{1}{C} \sum_i n_i (\Delta P_i)^m \quad (21)$$

Thus, cumulative fatigue damage is proportional to the sum of cycle ranges raised to a power.

2. Pseudo-Fatigue Damage Index

In this study, component-specific S–N data and stress conversion models were unavailable. Therefore, a pseudo-fatigue damage index was defined as:

$$D_{pseudo} = \sum_i c_i (\Delta P_i)^3 \quad (22)$$

where c_i represents the rainflow cycle count. The exponent of 3 was selected as a representative fatigue slope commonly used for pressure-loaded metallic components (Basquin, 1910; Downing, 2013). This formulation preserves the essential physics of fatigue accumulation:

- larger pressure cycles contribute disproportionately more damage;
- damage accumulates linearly with cycle count, and
- relative severity between operating periods is retained.

The index is used strictly as a relative severity metric and does not represent absolute fatigue life or failure probability.

Appendix B

Appendix B.1 Machine Learning Feature Definitions

This appendix summarises the features used in the machine learning models, along with their mathematical definitions and physical interpretations.

1. Statistical and Gradient-Based Features

Table 2 below defines and interprets each statistical and gradient-based feature.

Table 2. Statistical and Gradient -Based Features

Feature	Definition	Physical Interpretation
\bar{P}	Daily mean inlet pressure	Average upstream loading
σ_P	Daily standard deviation	Pressure variability
P_{min}, P_{max}	Daily min and max pressure	Operating envelope
R_P	$P_{max} - P_{min}$	Daily pressure swing
$\Delta\bar{P}$	Mean pressure increment	Net daily trend

2. Statistical and Gradient-Based Features

Table 3 below defines and interprets each statistical and gradient-based feature.

Table 3. Rainflow-Derived Features

Feature	Definition	Physical Interpretation
RF_{max}	Maximum cycle range	Most severe daily pressure cycle
RF_{mean}	Mean cycle range	Typical cyclic amplitude
RF_{big}	Cycles with $\Delta P > 0.5$ bar	Frequency of large cycles
D_{Pseudo}	$\sum_i c_i (\Delta P_i)^3$	Relative cyclic damage severity

Together, these features capture both overall inlet-pressure behaviour and fatigue-relevant cyclic characteristics.